

Table S3 Zircon U-Pb ages and trace element compositions of studied granites from the Mazongshan and Huaniushan units.

	Pb	Th	U	Common Pb	Th/U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	rho	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	Concordance
Analysis No.	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		Ratio	1sigma	Ratio	1sigma	Ratio	1sigma		Age (Ma)	1sigma	Age (Ma)	1sigma	Age (Ma)	1sigma	
16BS005-10	31.4	236	412	0.85	0.57	0.0611	0.0018	0.5395	0.0159	0.0638	0.0006	0.34	644	58.3	438	10.5	399	3.9	90%
16BS005-18	44.3	384	563	0.95	0.68	0.0598	0.0017	0.5358	0.0155	0.0643	0.0007	0.39	594	63.0	436	10.3	402	4.4	91%
16BS005-25	28.1	204	374	0.10	0.55	0.0600	0.0019	0.5327	0.0172	0.0640	0.0007	0.34	606	36.1	434	11.4	400	4.2	91%
16BS005-02	37.6	273	503	2.30	0.54	0.0591	0.0018	0.5315	0.0167	0.0648	0.0009	0.42	572	64.8	433	11.1	405	5.2	93%
16BS005-12	96.3	627	1265	2.33	0.50	0.0588	0.0015	0.5255	0.0140	0.0642	0.0007	0.41	561	53.7	429	9.3	401	4.3	93%
16BS005-16	23.3	166	307	0.00	0.54	0.0587	0.0020	0.5199	0.0179	0.0636	0.0007	0.30	567	74.1	425	12.0	397	4.0	93%
16BS005-21	32.8	271	420	0.00	0.65	0.0589	0.0021	0.5263	0.0179	0.0646	0.0007	0.34	561	77.8	429	11.9	404	4.5	93%
16BS005-23	30.3	178	416	0.38	0.43	0.0578	0.0019	0.5057	0.0167	0.0629	0.0006	0.28	520	69.4	416	11.3	394	3.5	94%
16BS005-04	29.5	217	394	0.57	0.55	0.0558	0.0017	0.4856	0.0152	0.0629	0.0007	0.33	443	75.0	402	10.4	393	4.0	97%
16BS005-17	34.0	254	450	1.17	0.57	0.0562	0.0018	0.4951	0.0147	0.0635	0.0006	0.32	457	70.4	408	10.0	397	3.7	97%
16BS005-09	25.0	202	325	0.73	0.62	0.0542	0.0019	0.4812	0.0171	0.0642	0.0007	0.31	389	79.6	399	11.7	401	4.4	99%
16BS005-20	39.2	215	470	6.21	0.46	0.0932	0.0030	0.8480	0.0274	0.0652	0.0007	0.35	1492	61.1	624	15.1	407	4.5	57%
16BS005-13	54.4	411	644	4.62	0.64	0.0794	0.0023	0.7165	0.0205	0.0648	0.0006	0.31	1183	56.9	549	12.1	405	3.4	69%
16BS005-24	25.2	267	284	2.06	0.94	0.0728	0.0027	0.6582	0.0242	0.0654	0.0006	0.26	1009	75.9	514	14.8	408	3.8	77%
16BS005-01	72.8	605	915	1.19	0.66	0.0683	0.0022	0.6001	0.0189	0.0633	0.0006	0.30	880	68.5	477	12.0	396	3.6	81%
16BS005-19	48.2	335	643	1.70	0.52	0.0656	0.0020	0.5743	0.0175	0.0626	0.0007	0.35	794	65.6	461	11.3	392	4.0	83%
16BS005-11	23.1	155	293	0.69	0.53	0.0664	0.0026	0.5922	0.0241	0.0645	0.0007	0.25	820	78.7	472	15.4	403	4.0	84%
16BS005-22	39.5	308	513	1.54	0.60	0.0618	0.0025	0.5446	0.0219	0.0633	0.0007	0.28	665	80.5	441	14.4	396	4.3	89%
16BS123-04	16.6	88.1	192	0.00	0.46	0.0537	0.0036	0.4986	0.0317	0.0662	0.0017	0.40	367	154	411	21	413	10	99%
16BS123-06	29.7	122	365	2.00	0.33	0.0570	0.0023	0.5010	0.0188	0.0659	0.0014	0.55	494	61.1	412	12.7	411	8.2	99%
16BS123-10	29.3	147	364	0.00	0.40	0.0548	0.0020	0.4981	0.0182	0.0661	0.0011	0.46	467	81.5	410	12.3	412	6.7	99%
16BS123-01	23.1	90.6	288	3.13	0.31	0.0568	0.0025	0.5092	0.0225	0.0659	0.0011	0.38	483	103	418	15	412	7	98%
16BS123-02	33.4	167	400	0.00	0.42	0.0549	0.0028	0.4918	0.0245	0.0658	0.0019	0.57	406	108	406	17	411	11	98%
16BS123-07	26.2	107	338	1.35	0.32	0.0568	0.0021	0.5118	0.0191	0.0662	0.0011	0.46	483	83.3	420	12.9	413	6.9	98%
16BS123-11	14.6	77.0	180	0.00	0.43	0.0539	0.0026	0.4833	0.0216	0.0660	0.0011	0.39	365	111	400	15	412	7	97%
16BS123-13	18.0	94.6	229	0.60	0.41	0.0534	0.0029	0.4793	0.0271	0.0651	0.0012	0.32	346	124	398	19	406	7	97%
16BS123-15	21.5	98.3	271	0.00	0.36	0.0535	0.0032	0.4806	0.0278	0.0651	0.0011	0.30	350	133	399	19	407	7	97%
16BS123-14	22.7	120.9	284	0.00	0.43	0.0527	0.0020	0.4773	0.0169	0.0656	0.0011	0.46	322	82.4	396	11.6	410	6.5	96%
16BS123-17	20.0	106	253	0.54	0.42	0.0575	0.0026	0.5186	0.0220	0.0654	0.0010	0.36	509	100	424	15	408	6	96%
16BS123-08	10.4	47.5	128	2.37	0.37	0.0510	0.0033	0.4678	0.0313	0.0655	0.0015	0.34	243	148	390	22	409	9	95%

	Pb	Th	U	Common Pb	Th/U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U		
Analysis No.	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		Ratio	1sigma	Ratio	1sigma	Ratio	1sigma	rho	Age (Ma)	1sigma	Age (Ma)	1sigma	Age (Ma)	1sigma	Concordance
16BS123-12	31.5	122	410	0.00	0.30	0.0582	0.0019	0.5262	0.0177	0.0653	0.0009	0.41	600	74.1	429	11.8	408	5.5	94%
16BS123-09	14.4	95.6	175	0.10	0.55	0.0598	0.0030	0.5351	0.0271	0.0651	0.0011	0.32	594	109	435	18	407	6	93%
16BS123-03	25.0	130	297	1.99	0.44	0.0586	0.0030	0.5452	0.0263	0.0656	0.0012	0.39	554	111	442	17	410	7	92%
16BS123-18	32.5	169	405	0.00	0.42	0.0604	0.0024	0.5459	0.0173	0.0656	0.0009	0.44	617	83.3	442	11.4	409	5.5	92%
16BS123-16	18.4	95.9	220	2.49	0.44	0.0645	0.0030	0.5767	0.0224	0.0660	0.0011	0.42	767	98.1	462	14.4	412	6.5	88%
16BS123-05	7.5	38.9	85	1.92	0.46	0.0670	0.0056	0.5800	0.0452	0.0655	0.0017	0.34	837	179	464	29	409	10	87%
16BS124-04	10.9	73.0	133	0.03	0.55	0.0567	0.0032	0.4887	0.0260	0.0644	0.0012	0.36	480	126	404	18	402	7	99%
16BS124-08	25.1	127	323	2.55	0.39	0.0555	0.0025	0.4943	0.0212	0.0654	0.0013	0.48	435	100	408	14	408	8	99%
16BS124-14	33.0	189	426	0.00	0.44	0.0547	0.0018	0.4872	0.0154	0.0648	0.0007	0.36	398	74.1	403	10.5	405	4.5	99%
16BS124-15	22.0	164	259	1.44	0.63	0.0547	0.0021	0.4962	0.0196	0.0654	0.0009	0.35	398	87.0	409	13.3	409	5.5	99%
16BS124-02	20.6	122	238	0.00	0.51	0.0523	0.0024	0.5057	0.0193	0.0653	0.0012	0.48	302	138	416	13	408	7	98%
16BS124-17	29.0	118	362	1.38	0.33	0.0544	0.0029	0.4839	0.0287	0.0654	0.0013	0.34	387	120	401	20	409	8	98%
16BS124-18	26.9	140	339	0.24	0.41	0.0533	0.0021	0.5060	0.0173	0.0653	0.0011	0.51	339	91.7	416	11.7	408	6.9	98%
16BS124-05	24.3	170	285	0.67	0.59	0.0534	0.0025	0.4767	0.0235	0.0651	0.0012	0.36	343	110	396	16	406	7	97%
16BS124-10	22.9	146	286	0.00	0.51	0.0575	0.0025	0.5075	0.0166	0.0649	0.0008	0.37	509	99.1	417	11.2	406	4.8	97%
16BS124-13	10.2	72.0	127	0.00	0.57	0.0576	0.0036	0.5062	0.0292	0.0647	0.0011	0.29	517	142	416	20	404	7	97%
16BS124-01	26.6	91.2	350	2.21	0.26	0.0551	0.0030	0.5146	0.0269	0.0652	0.0016	0.48	417	150	422	18	407	10	96%
16BS124-06	13.5	81.6	159	1.64	0.51	0.0526	0.0031	0.5102	0.0276	0.0647	0.0011	0.32	322	135	419	19	404	7	96%
16BS124-09	27.2	159	351	0.02	0.45	0.0573	0.0018	0.5089	0.0157	0.0646	0.0007	0.36	502	70.4	418	10.6	404	4.4	96%
16BS124-11	26.9	145	349	0.00	0.41	0.0577	0.0017	0.5187	0.0160	0.0650	0.0008	0.42	517	64.8	424	10.7	406	5.1	95%
16BS124-07	24.3	109	317	0.24	0.35	0.0586	0.0022	0.5283	0.0199	0.0656	0.0010	0.41	554	78.7	431	13.2	410	6.1	94%
16BS124-12	24.6	120	323	2.61	0.37	0.0604	0.0023	0.5293	0.0175	0.0641	0.0010	0.49	617	49.1	431	11.6	400	6.3	92%
16BS124-16	28.6	120	373	0.00	0.32	0.0623	0.0019	0.5554	0.0167	0.0651	0.0009	0.48	683	65.6	449	10.9	406	5.7	90%
16BS124-03	23.3	110	297	0.37	0.37	0.0653	0.0023	0.5821	0.0188	0.0653	0.0009	0.42	787	74.1	466	12.0	408	5.3	86%
16BS125-04	24.6	127	318	0.97	0.40	0.0554	0.0026	0.4968	0.0223	0.0658	0.0014	0.47	428	104	410	15	411	8	99%
16BS125-16	25.1	136	323	0.00	0.42	0.0551	0.0019	0.5045	0.0165	0.0661	0.0008	0.39	417	80.5	415	11.1	413	5.1	99%
16BS125-02	36.0	216	453	0.00	0.48	0.0545	0.0020	0.4908	0.0177	0.0656	0.0010	0.43	391	86.1	405	12.0	410	6.2	98%
16BS125-01	31.8	156	380	0.63	0.41	0.0565	0.0019	0.5149	0.0181	0.0659	0.0011	0.48	478	74.1	422	12.1	411	6.7	97%
16BS125-07	40.7	149	542	0.04	0.27	0.0574	0.0019	0.5241	0.0159	0.0666	0.0010	0.50	506	78.7	428	10.6	416	6.2	97%
16BS125-08	23.1	99	310	0.00	0.32	0.0566	0.0021	0.5135	0.0195	0.0659	0.0012	0.48	476	88.0	421	13.1	412	7.2	97%

	Pb	Th	U	Common Pb	Th/U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	rho	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U	Concordance
Analysis No.	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm		Ratio	1sigma	Ratio	1sigma	Ratio	1sigma		Age (Ma)	1sigma	Age (Ma)	1sigma	Age (Ma)	1sigma	
16BS125-10	26.1	138	343	2.09	0.40	0.0571	0.0024	0.5105	0.0206	0.0653	0.0012	0.46	494	94.4	419	13.9	408	7.4	97%
16BS125-13	30.1	141	380	1.18	0.37	0.0560	0.0021	0.5105	0.0181	0.0654	0.0012	0.51	454	116	419	12	408	7	97%
16BS125-17	12.1	60.1	160	0.00	0.38	0.0529	0.0032	0.4773	0.0287	0.0653	0.0013	0.32	324	134	396	20	408	8	97%
16BS125-11	30.7	152	401	0.00	0.38	0.0535	0.0020	0.4813	0.0176	0.0661	0.0012	0.49	350	83.3	399	12.1	413	7.2	96%
16BS125-15	23.4	107	294	5.72	0.36	0.0557	0.0029	0.5204	0.0224	0.0658	0.0009	0.31	443	117	425	15	411	5	96%
16BS125-18	27.5	134	361	0.00	0.37	0.0578	0.0020	0.5257	0.0184	0.0657	0.0009	0.38	524	77.8	429	12.3	410	5.3	95%
16BS125-05	32.0	158	396	1.41	0.40	0.0567	0.0022	0.5473	0.0180	0.0659	0.0012	0.54	480	85.2	443	11.8	411	7.0	92%
16BS125-09	19.1	81	255	0.00	0.32	0.0605	0.0023	0.5418	0.0198	0.0654	0.0010	0.42	633	82.2	440	13.0	409	6.0	92%
16BS125-06	33.3	165	428	0.55	0.39	0.0613	0.0021	0.5531	0.0174	0.0655	0.0010	0.50	650	75.9	447	11.4	409	6.3	91%
16BS125-03	33.3	137	434	1.91	0.31	0.0616	0.0021	0.5596	0.0184	0.0660	0.0010	0.47	659	70.4	451	12.0	412	6.2	90%
16BS125-12	24.8	104	329	0.00	0.32	0.0629	0.0023	0.5650	0.0199	0.0660	0.0012	0.50	706	75.0	455	12.9	412	7.0	90%
16BS125-14	23.0	95.4	300	2.17	0.32	0.0634	0.0024	0.5887	0.0223	0.0669	0.0011	0.43	724	279	470	14	417	7	88%
16BS117-17	22.5	106	294	3.06	0.36	0.0545	0.0020	0.4896	0.0175	0.0651	0.0007	0.32	391	81.5	405	12.0	407	4.5	99%
16BS117-18	22.9	87.2	314	0.06	0.28	0.0545	0.0019	0.4831	0.0173	0.0640	0.0007	0.31	391	84.3	400	11.9	400	4.2	99%
16BS117-05	25.1	133	301	1.29	0.44	0.0570	0.0024	0.5038	0.0222	0.0654	0.0015	0.53	500	96.3	414	15.0	408	9.3	98%
16BS117-13	25.4	120	333	1.68	0.36	0.0556	0.0019	0.4923	0.0172	0.0641	0.0009	0.42	435	77.8	406	11.7	401	5.8	98%
16BS117-14	27.8	110	358	1.21	0.31	0.0558	0.0023	0.5029	0.0200	0.0654	0.0010	0.39	443	127	414	14	408	6	98%
16BS117-09	20.4	97.8	265	0.00	0.37	0.0571	0.0033	0.5004	0.0285	0.0639	0.0012	0.33	494	130	412	19	399	7	96%
16BS117-16	33.4	159	435	0.00	0.36	0.0521	0.0017	0.4639	0.0149	0.0644	0.0008	0.39	300	75.9	387	10.4	403	4.9	96%
16BS117-11	19.3	74.8	254	2.69	0.29	0.0588	0.0026	0.5103	0.0218	0.0638	0.0012	0.43	561	98.1	419	14.7	399	7.1	95%
16BS117-01	21.0	85.4	267	0.68	0.32	0.0601	0.0028	0.5242	0.0227	0.0649	0.0012	0.43	606	101	428	15	405	7	94%
16BS117-12	24.5	89.6	321	2.15	0.28	0.0587	0.0023	0.5179	0.0200	0.0643	0.0010	0.41	567	82.4	424	13.4	402	6.1	94%
16BS117-08	13.6	46.3	178	0.79	0.26	0.0477	0.0025	0.4501	0.0194	0.0648	0.0011	0.40	83	128	377	14	405	7	93%
16BS117-03	24.2	96.2	318	0.00	0.30	0.0611	0.0024	0.5400	0.0192	0.0648	0.0009	0.38	643	85.2	438	12.6	405	5.3	92%
16BS117-04	29.5	98.5	401	1.63	0.25	0.0611	0.0024	0.5379	0.0202	0.0646	0.0011	0.45	643	80.5	437	13.3	403	6.5	91%
16BS117-06	15.2	55.1	203	2.76	0.27	0.0638	0.0041	0.5333	0.0311	0.0639	0.0023	0.63	744	137	434	21	399	14	91%
16BS117-02	21.1	99.1	276	2.30	0.36	0.0611	0.0023	0.5400	0.0196	0.0641	0.0009	0.38	643	79.6	438	12.9	401	5.3	90%
16BS117-10	22.5	109	282	1.38	0.39	0.0621	0.0026	0.5445	0.0202	0.0641	0.0010	0.41	677	88.9	441	13.3	401	5.9	90%
16BS117-15	23.9	97.0	293	1.42	0.33	0.0717	0.0026	0.6457	0.0219	0.0651	0.0009	0.42	977	74.1	506	13.5	406	5.6	78%
16BS117-07	10.6	48.1	175	0.60	0.27	0.0869	0.0040	0.7712	0.0348	0.0650	0.0012	0.42	1358	94.9	580	20.0	406	7.5	64%

Analysis No.	Pb ppm	Th ppm	U ppm	Common Pb ppm	Th/U	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb Ratio	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb 1sigma	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U Ratio	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U 1sigma	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U Ratio	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U 1sigma	rho	Age (Ma)	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²⁰⁶ Pb 1sigma	Age (Ma)	²⁰⁷ Pb/ ²³⁵ U 1sigma	Age (Ma)	²⁰⁶ Pb/ ²³⁸ U 1sigma	Concordance
16BS118-01	29.7	175	343	1.03	0.51	0.0514	0.0023	0.5153	0.0178	0.0639	0.0010	0.45	257	106	422	12	399	6	94%
16BS118-02	19.5	65.2	266	2.36	0.25	0.0574	0.0022	0.5107	0.0198	0.0644	0.0010	0.41	506	83.3	419	13.3	402	6.3	95%
16BS118-03	81.9	424	947	0.79	0.45	0.0537	0.0013	0.4846	0.0129	0.0654	0.0009	0.49	361	57.4	401	8.8	408	5.2	98%
16BS118-04	97.9	360	1278	1.62	0.28	0.0562	0.0015	0.5014	0.0142	0.0647	0.0012	0.67	457	59.3	413	9.6	404	7.4	97%
16BS118-07	74.9	555	949	0.00	0.58	0.0589	0.0015	0.5197	0.0126	0.0636	0.0007	0.43	565	53.7	425	8.4	397	4.0	93%
16BS118-08	32.5	187	395	0.42	0.47	0.0551	0.0033	0.4943	0.0219	0.0651	0.0009	0.30	413	133	408	15	407	5	99%
16BS118-05	28.8	255	333	0.12	0.76	0.0679	0.0024	0.6045	0.0200	0.0646	0.0009	0.40	865	73.0	480	12.7	403	5.2	82%
16BS118-06	38.8	241	447	1.13	0.54	0.0638	0.0025	0.5694	0.0238	0.0651	0.0017	0.61	744	83.3	458	15.4	407	10.1	88%
16BS119-01	266.8	89.4	3632	0.00	0.02	0.0536	0.0011	0.4708	0.0106	0.0635	0.0009	0.60	354	46.3	392	7.3	397	5.2	98%
16BS119-02	246.4	96.5	3664	1.10	0.03	0.0553	0.0012	0.4997	0.0118	0.0653	0.0011	0.74	428	48.1	412	8.0	408	6.9	99%
16BS119-05	52.0	174.4	707	0.98	0.25	0.0562	0.0017	0.5064	0.0154	0.0654	0.0010	0.50	461	66.7	416	10.4	408	6.0	98%
16BS119-09	42.0	289	483	0.00	0.60	0.0580	0.0019	0.5172	0.0178	0.0647	0.0011	0.48	532	76.8	423	11.9	404	6.5	95%
16BS119-10	31.7	134	420	4.26	0.32	0.0618	0.0020	0.5448	0.0161	0.0643	0.0010	0.53	733	73.1	442	10.6	402	6.1	90%
16BS119-12	44.0	157	584	9.52	0.27	0.0602	0.0025	0.5372	0.0185	0.0645	0.0013	0.57	609	90.7	437	12.2	403	7.7	91%
16BS119-15	26.5	94.1	359	0.00	0.26	0.0584	0.0021	0.5209	0.0181	0.0650	0.0010	0.43	543	77.8	426	12.1	406	5.9	95%
16BS119-16	73.5	191	1032	1.69	0.19	0.0566	0.0014	0.5049	0.0117	0.0648	0.0008	0.50	476	47.2	415	7.9	404	4.6	97%
16BS119-17	25.8	146	331	0.21	0.44	0.0615	0.0021	0.5466	0.0176	0.0646	0.0008	0.37	657	72.2	443	11.6	403	4.6	90%
16BS119-18	97.6	210	1314	0.00	0.16	0.0549	0.0021	0.5331	0.0166	0.0655	0.0009	0.45	409	89.8	434	11.0	409	5.5	94%
16BS119-06	92.6	251.7	1214	7.17	0.21	0.0739	0.0027	0.6639	0.0186	0.0653	0.0011	0.60	1039	73.0	517	11.4	408	6.7	76%
16BS119-08	14.1	71.4	206	0.00	0.35	0.0869	0.0038	0.6601	0.0252	0.0559	0.0011	0.52	1358	85.2	515	15.4	351	6.8	62%
16BS119-04	48.1	266	577	5.57	0.46	0.0767	0.0025	0.6731	0.0204	0.0642	0.0012	0.63	1122	60.2	523	12.4	401	7.5	73%

Note: Data in grey means their concordance is below 90%, which is not used to calculate.